

Appendix A. Proof of Proposition 1

We solve the non-cooperative game using backward induction.

Step 1: Recycler's technology investment decision. Given collection prices (p_M, p_R) , the recycler R chooses k to maximize Π_R^N in Equation 7. Taking the first-order derivative with respect to k :

$$\frac{\partial \Pi_R^N}{\partial k} = \theta(\alpha p_R - \beta p_M) - ck = 0 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Solving for k , we obtain the optimal conversion rate:

$$k^N(p_M, p_R) = \frac{\theta(\alpha p_R - \beta p_M)}{c} \quad (\text{A1})$$

Substituting (A1) into Π_R^N , the recycler's profit becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_R^N = & (s - p_R - m - \mu_R)(\alpha p_R - \beta p_M) + (w - m)(\alpha p_M - \beta p_R) \\ & + \frac{\theta^2(\alpha p_R - \beta p_M)^2}{2c} - p_c [e(\alpha - \beta)(p_M + p_R) - G] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A2})$$

Step 2: Price competition equilibrium. Using the profit functions Π_M^N and Π_R^N , we derive the reaction functions by taking first-order partial derivatives with respect to p_M and p_R , respectively, and setting them equal to zero:

$$\frac{\partial \Pi_M^N}{\partial p_M} = (\theta k - p_M - w - \mu_M + s)\alpha - (\alpha p_M - \beta p_R) = 0 \quad (\text{A3})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \Pi_R^N}{\partial p_R} = & (s - p_R - m - \mu_R)\alpha + \theta \alpha k^N - \alpha p_R + (w - m)(-\beta) \\ & - p_c e(\alpha - \beta) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A4})$$

Substituting k^N from (A1) into (A4), and solving the system of (A3)-(A4) simultaneously, we obtain the equilibrium collection prices p_M^{N*} and p_R^{N*} , which are given by Equations (9) and (10) in Proposition 1. Substituting these equilibrium prices back into (A1) yields k^{N*} in Equation (8). The equilibrium collection quantities and profits follow directly from substituting the equilibrium values into the profit functions. This completes the proof. \square

Appendix B. Proof of Proposition 2

We compute the characteristic functions for each coalition using the maximin principle.

(1) Coalition $\{M\}$. The characteristic function is:

$$V_{p_M, p_R}(\{M\}) = \max_{n \in [0,1]} \min_{k \in [0,1]} \{\Pi_M\} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Since $\Pi_M = (\theta k + s - p_M - w - \mu_M)(\alpha p_M - \beta p_R) - (1 - n)\frac{ck^2}{2}$ and $(\alpha p_M - \beta p_R) \geq 0$, for any given n , the term is minimized when $k = 0$. Maximizing over $n \in [0, 1]$ yields $n^* = 1$, which eliminates the investment cost term. Therefore:

$$V_{p_M, p_R}(\{M\}) = (s - p_M - w - \mu_M)(\alpha p_M - \beta p_R) \quad (\text{B1})$$

(2) Coalition $\{R\}$. The characteristic function is:

$$V_{p_M, p_R}(\{R\}) = \max_{k \in [0,1]} \{\Pi_R\} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Setting $n = 1$ (the recycler bears all costs) and taking the first-order derivative with respect to k :

$$\frac{\partial \Pi_R}{\partial k} = \theta(\alpha p_R - \beta p_M) - ck = 0 \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Solving yields $k^* = \frac{\theta(\alpha p_R - \beta p_M)}{c}$. Substituting into Π_R :

$$V_{p_M, p_R}(\{R\}) = \frac{(s - p_R - m - \mu_R)(\alpha p_R - \beta p_M) + (w - m)(\alpha p_M - \beta p_R)}{2c} - p_c [e(\alpha - \beta)(p_M + p_R) - G] \quad (\text{B.2})$$

(3) Grand coalition $\{M, R\}$. The characteristic function is:

$$V_{p_M, p_R}(\{M, R\}) = \max_{k \in [0, 1]} \{\Pi_M + \Pi_R\} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Taking the first-order derivative:

$$\frac{\partial(\Pi_M + \Pi_R)}{\partial k} = \theta(\alpha p_M - \beta p_R) + \theta(\alpha p_R - \beta p_M) - ck = 0 \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Solving yields $k^* = \frac{\theta(\alpha - \beta)(p_M + p_R)}{c}$. Substituting:

$$V_{p_M, p_R}(\{M, R\}) = \frac{(s - p_M - m - \mu_M)(\alpha p_M - \beta p_R) + (s - p_R - m - \mu_R)(\alpha p_R - \beta p_M)}{2c} - p_c [e(\alpha - \beta)(p_M + p_R) - G] \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Equations (B1)-(B3) correspond to the characteristic functions stated in Proposition ???. This completes the proof.

□

Appendix C. Proof of Proposition 3

From Proposition 2, we compute the surplus from forming the grand coalition:

$$\begin{aligned} & V_{p_M, p_R}(\{M, R\}) - V_{p_M, p_R}(\{M\}) - V_{p_M, p_R}(\{R\}) \\ &= \frac{\theta^2(\alpha - \beta)^2(p_M + p_R)^2}{2c} - \frac{\theta^2(\alpha p_R - \beta p_M)^2}{2c} \\ &= \frac{\theta^2}{2c}(\alpha p_M - \beta p_R)[(\alpha p_M - \beta p_R) + 2(\alpha p_R - \beta p_M)] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C1})$$

Since $\alpha > \beta > 0$ by assumption, we have $(\alpha p_M - \beta p_R) \geq 0$ and $(\alpha p_R - \beta p_M) \geq 0$. Additionally, $\theta > 0$ and $c > 0$. Therefore, the right-hand side of (C1) is always non-negative. Hence:

$$V_{p_M, p_R}(\{M, R\}) \geq V_{p_M, p_R}(\{M\}) + V_{p_M, p_R}(\{R\}) \quad (\text{C.1})$$

which establishes superadditivity. Furthermore, the marginal contribution of each player increases with the size of the coalition, satisfying the convexity condition. This completes the proof. □

Appendix D. Proof of Proposition 4

Having established the characteristic functions and Shapley value allocations $\varphi_M(p_M, p_R)$ and $\varphi_R(p_M, p_R)$ in Section 3.3, we now solve the non-cooperative price competition stage.

Step 1: Concavity verification. Taking second-order partial derivatives of φ_M and φ_R with respect to their respective prices:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \varphi_M}{\partial p_M^2} = -2\alpha + \frac{\theta^2(\alpha^2 - 2\alpha\beta)}{2c} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial^2 \varphi_R}{\partial p_R^2} = -2\alpha + \frac{\theta^2(2\alpha^2 - 2\alpha\beta + \beta^2)}{2c} \quad (\text{D.1})$$

To ensure the strict concavity of the profit allocation functions (i.e., both second-order derivatives are negative), the parameters must satisfy the conditions: $4c\alpha > \theta^2(\alpha^2 - 2\alpha\beta)$ and $4c\alpha > \theta^2(2\alpha^2 - 2\alpha\beta + \beta^2)$. Assuming the investment cost coefficient c is sufficiently large, these concavity conditions hold.

Step 2: First-order conditions. Setting the first-order partial derivatives to zero:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \varphi_M}{\partial p_M} = [\theta^2(\alpha^2 - 2\alpha\beta) - 4c\alpha]p_M + [\theta^2(\alpha^2 - \alpha\beta + \beta^2) + 2c\beta]p_R + 2c\alpha(s - w - \mu_M) = 0 \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_R}{\partial p_R} = [\theta^2(\alpha^2 - 3\alpha\beta + \beta^2) + 2c\beta]p_M + [\theta^2(2\alpha^2 - 2\alpha\beta + \beta^2) - 4c\alpha]p_R + 2c[\alpha(s - m - \mu_R) - \beta(w - m)] - 2cp_c e(\alpha - \beta) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (\text{D1})$$

Step 3: Solving the reaction functions. Solving the linear system (D1) yields the equilibrium collection prices p_M^{C*} and p_R^{C*} , which are given by Equations (27) and (28) in Proposition 4.

Step 4: Optimal conversion rate and R&D investment sharing proportion. Substituting p_M^{C*} and p_R^{C*} into the grand coalition's optimal k :

$$k^{C*} = \frac{\theta(\alpha - \beta)(p_M^{C*} + p_R^{C*})}{c} \quad (\text{D.2})$$

The optimal R&D investment sharing proportion n^{C*} is derived by equating the marginal contributions and solving for n , yielding the expression in Proposition 4.

The equilibrium Shapley value allocations φ_M^{C*} and φ_R^{C*} follow from substituting the equilibrium prices into the Shapley value formulas. This completes the proof. \square